

Efficient treatment of high-salinity aquaculture effluents through synergistic membrane distillation and VUV/UVC photolysis

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ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Xing Yang

Keywords:

Aquaculture
Advanced oxidation
Zero-liquid discharge
Water reuse
Circular economy

ABSTRACT

Effluents from mariculture facilities typically marked contain high salinity and organic loadings, including anti-parasitic chemicals such as formaldehyde. The direct discharge of such effluents poses serious environmental risks, thus requiring the development of sustainable methods for their treatment. Within this context, a novel approach based on the synergistic integration of thermally driven membrane distillation (MD) and vacuum-ultraviolet/ultraviolet-C (VUV/UVC) photolysis is proposed for the treatment of highly polluted saline water without the need of intensive pretreatments or chemical additives. In this specific work, the performances of the proposed integrated treatment process were explored for inland mariculture effluent. The MD system was able to reclaim 90 % of the effluent as distilled water. Concurrently, salts in the MD concentrate were recovered. The subsequent polishing of the MD permeate solution via VUV/UVC photolysis allowed the abatement of the volatiles present in the MD permeate, bringing the concentrations of formaldehyde and total organic carbon (TOC) below the detection limits (0.5 mg L⁻¹ for both techniques) within 20 min of treatment. The novel integrated system improves the purity of the recycled water and serves as an example of sustainable mariculture effluent management, advancing towards zero-liquid discharge within this field.

1. Introduction

In 2023, aquaculture production had soared to approximately 95.8 million tons [1,2]. Salty water aquaculture (mariculture) occupies the 29 % of the global aquaculture market, but it reaches 85 % in Europe [3] and about 60 % in China [4]. In densely populated fish farming facilities, the routine introduction of fish feeds, pharmaceuticals, and other chemical products can significantly impact the environment [5]. Consequently, the effect of the mariculture industry on ocean water quality cannot be overlooked. Inland salty water aquaculture offers multiple benefits compared to offshore farming, such as significantly lower risks of disease transmission and escape of farmed species into natural waters, along with improved control over the farming environment at the benefit of fish wellbeing [6]. Moreover, it allows the deployment of a series of technologies for the treatment of the fish farm effluent before returning it to the ocean. However, mariculture effluents are rich in nutrients, organics, and characterized by high salinity levels [7], posing a challenge for their treatment [8,9]. The release of these

untreated effluents into coastal regions can lead to pollution, eutrophication, and eventually deterioration of the marine ecosystem [10]. Hence, there is an urgent need for innovative technologies specifically designed to efficiently manage and possibly reuse mariculture effluents, for the sustainable growth of the mariculture industry.

In recent years, membrane technologies have emerged as a promising additional purification method after the biological treatments in different types of fish farms [6]. Specifically, reverse osmosis (RO) is one of the most used technologies in desalination applications. However, two aspects limit the effective installation of RO: (i) the energy-efficiency of RO is compromised by the increase in osmotic pressure during the filtration process [11,12], and (ii) water recovery rates typically vary between 35 %–85 %, depending on the feed water characteristics, thus producing a brine stream, the disposal of which represents a significant environmental challenge [12,13]. In this context, membrane distillation (MD), which is a thermally driven membrane process, offers a viable alternative for desalination. MD has the advantage of higher water recovery rates and nearly complete salt rejection

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.106042>

Received 14 May 2024; Received in revised form 11 August 2024; Accepted 21 August 2024

Available online 24 August 2024

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compared to RO [14]. The process uses a hydrophobic macroporous membrane to separate the feed solution from the permeate [15]. The feed is heated to create a temperature gradient across the membrane, allowing only water vapor to pass through the hydrophobic membrane pores, condensing on the permeate side [16,17]. This method allows concentrating the feed solution up to the saturation point for potential solute precipitation, thus facilitating the extraction of valuable minerals or molecules from the concentrate [18,19].

While MD is highly effective at retaining non-volatile components in the feed, its inability to reject volatile compounds poses a significant challenge [20], especially in mariculture systems where such compounds frequently accumulate. One example is formaldehyde (HCHO), which is widely used in aquaculture as a disinfectant to control parasites and fungal infections [21,22]. It is widely recognized that discharging formaldehyde-rich effluents can damage the marine ecosystem [23]. Additionally, off-odor and potentially harmful volatiles could compromise the characteristics of the permeate, preventing its reuse in potential downstream applications, such as land irrigation, hydroponics, or process water.

Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) have gained popularity for the abatement of organic contaminants in water. AOPs rely on the generation of hydroxyl radicals (OH•), which oxidize the organic pollutants into water and carbon dioxide [24]. Yet, most of the AOPs (e.g., Fenton-based processes) require additional chemical input, potentially increasing the cost for water treatment and causing secondary pollution [25,26]. On the other hand, vacuum-ultraviolet/ultraviolet-C (VUV/UVC) technologies have seen increased application in water disinfection and detoxification, both in fish farming and drinking water treatment [27–30]. Compared to the traditional AOPs, the VUV/UVC photolysis process has simpler implementation and functions without the need for additional chemicals [31]. VUV devices emit photons typically within the 100 to 200 nm range, often in conjunction with UV-C irradiation at 254 nm. Extensive research has demonstrated the efficacy of VUV/UVC in the removal of organic pollutants from water [28,29,32–34], various industrial effluents can be processed including food, textile, and oil-based industries [35,36]. VUV/UVC photolysis has proven effective in the abatement of various micropollutants such as pharmaceuticals, recalcitrant aldehydes, humic substances, chlorinated hydrocarbons, and quaternary ammonium compounds [28,37].

At the best of our knowledge, this study presents the first synergistic integration of MD with VUV/UVC photolysis in treating mariculture effluent. A conceptual scheme of the proposed integrated system is shown in Fig. 1. In this process, the saltwater aquaculture effluent is treated through a drum filter (primary treatment) and then undergoes the denitrification and nitrification biological (secondary) treatments. After these conventional steps, the saltwater aquaculture effluent is sent to the proposed integrated system of this work, comprised of an MD unit and a VUV-UVC unit. The MD system can simultaneously produce (i) a permeate with a salinity potentially equal to that of distilled water and (ii) a concentrate with a higher salinity from which it is possible to recover minerals/salts via downstream crystallization technologies. Considered the MD permeate, traces of volatile organic contaminants can remain since they cannot be retained by the MD system. Thus, here we propose to polish this stream by a VUV/UVC irradiation unit, producing ultrapure water. By combining the distinct strengths of both MD and VUV/UVC systems, the study presents a feasible strategy for achieving zero-liquid discharge (ZLD), enhancing the sustainability of mariculture operations [38].

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and chemicals

Samples of mariculture effluent were obtained from an inland facility that uses Red Sea water, characterized by a salinity of 36–41 Practical Salinity Units (PSU). The MD process utilized a commercial hollow polypropylene fiber module (Microdyn-Nadir, MD 020 CP 2 N), which features an active filtration area of 0.1 m² and an average pore size of 0.2 μm. Formaldehyde (HCHO, 37 wt% in water, Sigma-Aldrich) was added as a pollutant to the water sample, and Fluoral P (97 %, Sigma-Aldrich) was employed to detect the permeate HCHO concentration. These chemicals were used without further purification. Detailed descriptions of the effluent's specific parameters, the experimental setup, and the characterization methods are provided in the subsequent sections.

Fig. 1. Conceptual scheme of the proposed integrated system for the treatment of saltwater aquaculture effluent to obtain ultrapure water and salts.

2.2. Mariculture effluent

Table 1 presents the characteristics of the effluent sample, such as its chemical composition and concentrations of cations and anions. Furthermore, to model possible contamination during the fish farming, the effluent was spiked with HCHO (20 mg L⁻¹) to facilitate the evaluation of the effectiveness of the MD and VUV/UVC systems in the removal of contaminants during the abatement tests.

2.3. Membrane distillation

For this study, a laboratory-scale direct contact membrane distillation (DCMD) system using a commercial hollow fiber module was utilized. Details of the system configuration are described in earlier studies [34]. Initially, the volumes of the feed and permeate solutions were 2 L and 0.7 L, respectively. The feed solution was heated up before entering the MD module (more specifically, at 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C to evaluate the MD performances in three different scenarios), while the permeate tank was cooled at 15 °C. The feed solution flowed inside the hollow fibers, while the permeate stream traveled around the exterior of the fibers. Both streams were propelled at a rate of 20 L h⁻¹ by a Masterflex thermostatic peristaltic pump. A countercurrent flow setup was employed to optimize the temperature differential across the membrane. Temperatures at both the inlet and outlet of the feed and permeate sides were recorded using digital thermometers from Mettler Toledo throughout the experiments. The MD system's permeability was tracked by observing the increase in water weight in the permeate tank, which was measured with a digital scale. Additionally, the feed pH level and the permeate conductivity were determined using a MeterLab (CDM210) conductometer and data was recorded through a MATLAB program. The rejection of the membrane was calculated using Eq. (1), where C_p and C_f represent the conductivity of the permeate and feed water from the MD process, respectively.

$$\text{Rejection}(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{C_p}{C_f}\right) 100 \quad (1)$$

The water recovery factor was calculated using Eq. (2), where $V_{p,t}$ represents the permeate volume at a certain filtration time, V_f denotes the initial feed volume, and $V_{p,0}$ indicates the initial permeate volume.

$$\text{Recovery factor}(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{V_{p,t} - V_{p,0}}{V_f}\right) 100 \quad (2)$$

2.4. VUV/UVC treatment

The experiments on HCHO degradation discussed in this study were performed using a custom-built VUV/UVC photolysis reactor. Before initiating the experiments, the permeate from the MD process was filled with distilled water to achieve a total volume of 3.5 L, accommodating the system's volume constraints prior to starting circulation. A previous publication provided a detailed description of the reactor's design [34]. In brief, the reactor setup included a stainless-steel cylindrical feed tank

Table 1
Composition of the inland mariculture effluent fed to the MD system.

Parameters	Values	Ions	Concentration (mg L ⁻¹)
pH	8.1	Na ⁺	13,288
Conductivity	56.6 mS cm ⁻¹	K ⁺	508
Salinity	37.6 PSU	Mg ²⁺	1653
		Ca ²⁺	601
Total dissolved carbon	26.9 mg L ⁻¹		
Inorganic carbon	21.3 mg L ⁻¹	HCO ₃ ⁻	108
Organic carbon	5.6 mg L ⁻¹	Cl ⁻	22,582
Total nitrogen	5.5 mg L ⁻¹	SO ₄ ²⁻	2784
(Ammonia)	(1.2 mg L ⁻¹)	NO ₃ ⁻	21
Phosphates (as P)	2.4 mg L ⁻¹	PO ₄ ³⁻	1.0

linked to a photolysis reactor housing an amalgam VUV/UVC lamp (1050 mm × 19 mm) [34]. A centrifugal pump circulated the solution at a flow rate of approximately 2 L per minute, and a cooling system maintained a constant ambient temperature. The lamp was set to generate UVC and VUV light in a 4:1 ratio, producing radiation fluxes of 56 W for UVC and 14 W for VUV. Each degradation trial lasted 64 min, during which water samples were periodically taken for analysis.

2.5. Characterization of water and salt samples

The salinity and pH levels of both the feed and permeate solutions were determined using a MeterLab (CDM210) conductivity meter. The concentration of HCHO was assessed through the Hantzsch reaction involving β-diketone, specifically 4-amino-3-pentene-2-one (Fluoral-P) [39]. In this reaction, HCHO interacts with Fluoral-P, resulting in the formation of 3,5-diacetyl-1,4-dihydrolutidine, which can be detected using spectrometric and fluorimetric methods. For the analysis, Fluoral P (Sigma, Denmark) was dissolved in acetonitrile and subsequently added to samples that had been adjusted to a pH of 4 using phosphate buffer. The absorbance at 412 nm and fluorescence (Excitation/Emission at 485/535 nm) were measured after 30 min using a Thermo Scientific™ GENESYS™ 20 Visible Spectrophotometer and a Perkin Elmer Victor X2 multilabel plate reader, respectively. The determination of HCHO levels remained accurate with sodium chloride concentrations in the samples up to 28 ppt, showing no interference.

The HCHO/water molar ratio in the permeating vapor was calculated from the ratios of the corresponding transmembrane molar fluxes (J). These were obtained from the changes of their concentration in the permeate and the increment of permeate volume in a specific time interval (Eq. (3)).

$$J_i = \frac{C_{i,t2} \cdot V_{p,t2} - C_{i,t1} \cdot V_{p,t1}}{\Delta t \cdot A} \quad (3)$$

In order to recover the salt crystals for XRD and ICP characterization, the filtration experiment was stopped. The feed was collected, cooled at room temperature and centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 10 min. The recovered crystals were further dried overnight and then dried at room temperature. An optical microscope (ZEISS, Axiolab 5) was utilized to examine a water sample from the feed solution to study salt crystal formation during the MD process. The structure of the crystals collected from the concentrate was analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) on an Empyrean XRD system by PANalytical, equipped with a monochromator and Cu Kα radiation (1.5406 Å). Diffractograms were recorded within a 2θ range of 5° to 75° at 40 kV and a scan rate of 0.13° s⁻¹. At the same time, the composition of the salt crystals was ascertained by dissolving the dried salts into DI water to achieve a 1 g L⁻¹ of concentration, and the resultant cation concentration in the solution was measured using an ICP (PerkinElmer® Optima 8000 Optical Emission Spectrometer). Calibration of the ICP instrument was conducted using standards from PlasmaCAL Q.C. No 4 (SCP Science).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Membrane distillation of the mariculture discharge

First, we assessed the desalination performance of the hollow fiber membrane distillation module on mariculture effluent. Prior to conducting the experiments, we passed the effluent water samples through a paper filter (50 μm) to eliminate any large, suspended particles. Each MD test began with a 2 L of effluent solution. Regarding the water recovery factors, these were recorded over the duration of filtration in the experiments, as shown in Fig. 2a. The water recovery factor exhibited a steady, almost linear increase over time, achieving levels between 80 % and 90 % across the three temperature settings. Notably, the water recovery factors increased with temperature as well due to higher water flux, thereby reducing the time required to reach the pre-determined

Fig. 2. MD treatment of the salty aquaculture effluent fed at 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C: (a) water recovery as a function of the filtration time and (b) permeate flux as a function of the water recovery factor.

water recovery factor at elevated temperatures. Hence, the water fluxes of the MD system at different operational temperatures over time were calculated and reported in Fig. 2b. Overall, the water flux was fairly consistent across different temperatures. The permeate fluxes across the membrane were roughly 0.6, 1.5, and 2.6 L m⁻² h⁻¹, when the temperature of the feed tank was set at 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C, respectively. This trend is expected, as the primary driver of water permeation in this context is the vapor pressure differential created by the temperature gradient across the MD membrane. Over time, a slight decrease in permeate fluxes was observed, due to the increasing osmotic pressure of the concentrating feed solution and the precipitation of salt crystals at the feed side of the membrane. At the ending stage of the MD process of each operating temperature, crystal formation was noticeable in the feed solution. A comprehensive analysis of these crystals is detailed in the subsequent section.

The MD process demonstrated significant rejection of salt ions at the tested temperatures. Changes in permeate conductivity over time are depicted in Fig. 3a. Although MD theoretically achieves 100% rejection, the observed permeate conductivity across the tested temperatures was approximately 100 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. This value is almost negligible when compared to the conductivity of the feed (42,000 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$), suggesting that the majority of salt ions were retained by the MD process. Nonetheless, the trend in permeate conductivity typically began by increasing initially and then decreasing over time. It's notable that the peak permeate conductivity slightly increased with higher feed temperatures. The highest recorded permeate conductivity values were 100 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, 107 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, and 113 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ at temperatures of 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C, respectively. This increase in conductivity may be attributed to the transportation of ionizable volatile substances, such as ammonia, low molecular weight amines and organic acids evidenced by the presence of values of total nitrogen (5.5 mg L⁻¹) and ammonia (1.2 mg L⁻¹) as reported in Table 1 for the effluent. With rising temperatures, the volatile

components' vapor pressure also increases, leading to a higher concentration of these conductive volatile components in the permeate and, consequently, increased conductivity. Over time, most of the ionizable volatile components from the feed pass through the membrane. Therefore, after a certain filtration time, the evaporation rate of water surpasses that of the other volatile components, diluting the permeate. This explains the decrease in conductivity in the later stage of the MD process, observed in Fig. 3a. This reduction is likely due to the diluting effect of the water, which progressively lowers the concentration of ionizable components in the permeate.

In the mariculture industry, HCHO is widely used as an antifungal, antibacterial and antiparasitic agent. Fig. 3b shows how the concentration of HCHO in the permeate changes over time at three different operating temperatures. Generally, the MD process has demonstrated limited effectiveness in retaining HCHO, with its final concentration in the permeate recorded at 7.1, 15.8, and 10.9 mg L⁻¹ at temperatures of 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C, respectively. The concentrations of HCHO in the permeate solutions developed almost linearly over time, suggesting a fairly consistent rate of HCHO evaporation from the feed solution. The net flux of HCHO through the membrane was calculated based on the concentrations in the permeate, considering the initial volume of demineralized (DI) water (700 mL) and is depicted in Fig. 4a. It is evident that the HCHO transmembrane flux increases with the feed temperature, which can be considered as a consequence of the increased vapor pressure. Moreover, the transmembrane flux of HCHO increases more sharply than in the case of water (Fig. 4b). As a consequence, the composition of the vapors permeating through the MD membrane becomes richer in HCHO. Indeed, the HCHO/water mol/mol ratio in the permeating vapor increases from 5.0×10^{-6} in the experiment with the feed at 40 °C to 5.0×10^{-6} in the filtration experiment with the feed at 40 °C to 9.7×10^{-6} in the filtration experiment with the feed at 70 °C. The latter value is close to the HCHO/water mol/mol ratio in the feed solution, i.e. 1.2×10^{-5} . This suggests that HCHO evaporates more slowly than water vapor within the tested temperature range, leading to its partial retention.

3.2. VUV/UVC photolysis

As mentioned in the previous section, the membrane showed limited effectiveness in retaining HCHO. We collected post-MD permeates with HCHO concentrations ranging from 4 mg L⁻¹ (at a feed tank temperature of 40 °C) to 8 mg L⁻¹ (at 70 °C). Consequently, we suggest using VUV/UVC photolysis for the oxidative removal of HCHO in the permeate. Typically, the breakdown of HCHO results from the generation of hydroxyl free radicals through the homolysis of water and oxygen molecules induced by VUV/UVC irradiation, as demonstrated in Eqs. (4), (5) and (6) [40]. The possible byproducts of this photolysis include

Fig. 3. Permeate conductivity (a) and HCHO concentration (b) in the permeate during membrane distillation experiment at feed operating temperatures of 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C over time.

Fig. 4. Characteristics of the vapors permeating through the membrane at the MD feed tank operating temperatures of 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C: (a) average formaldehyde (HCHO) transmembrane molar flux, (b) average water transmembrane molar flux, (c) mol/mol ratio of HCHO and water in the permeating vapor.

hydrogen, hydroxide, and oxygen free radicals, as well as protons and electrons. These reactive species are effective not only in degrading organic micropollutants but also in reducing potential heavy metal ions, thus enhancing the effectiveness of the VUV/UVC water treatment.

To evaluate the HCHO degradation efficiency of the VUV/UVC photolysis reactor, water samples were taken at regular intervals during irradiation. The abatement of HCHO within the reactor, denoted as C/C_0 , is depicted in Fig. 5a in relation to the irradiation time. Generally, the VUV/UVC reactor demonstrates high effectiveness in removing HCHO, with exponential abatement time profiles. The degradation rate of HCHO for the permeate obtained from MD with feed at 40 °C are slightly higher than the samples obtained from 55 °C and 70 °C. This difference is attributed to the lower initial HCHO concentration,

approximately 4.0 mg L⁻¹ in the 40 °C sample, while the starting concentrations for the 55 °C and 70 °C samples are 8.0 mg L⁻¹ and 7.3 mg L⁻¹, respectively. With a 6.25 J cm⁻² of irradiation, the HCHO degradation reached 97 %, 73 %, and 77 %. After 8 min, the permeate obtained from temperatures of 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C was analyzed. Beyond 16 min, HCHO concentrations in all three permeates dropped below the detection threshold of 0.5 mg L⁻¹. The pH levels in the reactor water were also tracked during the VUV/UVC photolysis process, as illustrated in Fig. 5b. The pH trend mirrored the HCHO degradation curve. Initially, at 0 min, the pH of permeates from various temperatures ranged between 7.3 and 7.6. Over time, a gradual decrease in pH was noted, falling to about 6.7 within the first 10 min of the experiment and stabilizing between 6.5 and 6.6 for the remainder. This pH reduction can be attributed to the formation of oxidation intermediates such as formic acid and CO₂ resulting from HCHO breakdown. Moreover, the generation of H⁺ ions during photolysis, as indicated in Eq. (2), also contributes to the lowering of the pH. On the other hand, no noticeable changes in conductivity were observed for any of the permeate samples during the photolysis process, all values remained below 100 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 5. HCHO abatement by VUV/UVC photolysis for the permeates recovered from the MD unit fed at 40 °C, 55 °C and 70 °C with mariculture effluent: (a) change of the relative HCHO concentration (C/C_0) and (b) pH variation as a function of the irradiation time. Section (c) shows the concentration of HCHO and of the total organic carbon (TOC) in the permeate from the MD fed at 40 °C at different irradiation time.

The in-situ measurement of HCHO concentration in the photolysis reactor for the permeate samples obtained from all temperatures, as well as the total organic carbon (TOC) levels in permeate from MD fed at 40 °C, are illustrated in Fig. 5c for different irradiation time. Like the observed trends in HCHO concentration, the TOC in the permeate samples also exhibits an exponential decrease. Initially, TOC is 4.2 mg L⁻¹, but after about 40 min it is reduced to below our limit of quantification, namely 0.5 mg L⁻¹. These results demonstrate the efficacy of the VUV/UVC photolysis process in mineralizing the organic volatiles which are dissolved in the MD permeate, such as HCHO.

3.3. Potential for salt recovery

During the MD process, the precipitation of salts becomes evident when the saturation point has been reached in the feed. Thus, MD proves effective not only in producing distilled water on the permeate side but also in recovering molecules and minerals from the concentrate. To explore the possibility of recovering salt crystals from the feed in a zero liquid discharge scenario, crystal formation during the MD process was monitored using an optical microscope. Furthermore, the salt crystals

produced in the MD experiment were examined using ICP and XRD techniques. The feed sample at an operating temperature of 70 °C was periodically examined under the microscope every 15 min, starting from when a recovery factor of 77 % was achieved, to track crystal formation. Microscope images shown in Fig. 6 reveal two types of crystals in the feed solution, distinguishable before and after reaching a recovery factor of 83 %. The crystals formed before achieving an 83 % recovery factor exhibit no distinct geometric shapes. It can be inferred that salts with low solubilities, such as calcium sulfates and carbonates, begin to precipitate at this stage [41]. As crystal formation progresses, this becomes more apparent, especially for the initial type of salt crystals noted at a recovery factor of 83 %. Beyond this point, cubic-shaped crystals start to emerge in the feed solution, a shape typically associated with the formation of NaCl. [42] Over the next 30 min, as the recovery increases from 86 % to 92 %, these crystals continue to grow and agglomerate, making their recovery more feasible.

The structure of the recovered salt samples was investigated by XRD analysis. As depicted in 6, the predominant salt crystals identified are NaCl and gypsum (CaSO₄·2H₂O). Specifically, the peak positions of crystals from the feed solutions at 55 °C and 70 °C correspond

Fig. 6. The salt crystals formation microscope image of the inorganic salt crystals in the MD feed at 70 °C for recovery factors ranging between 77 and 92 %.

predominantly to halite whereas the sample obtained from the filtration tests at 40 °C presents mainly the peaks corresponding to the characteristic gypsum reflections. Phase quantification was performed on the HighScore Plus software, revealing that the NaCl/gypsum ratio increases from 0.39 to 2.3 when the recovery factor raised from 79 % to 87 % (Fig. 7).

The composition of the recovered salts samples was analyzed by ICP analysis to confirm the crystal phases observed at the diffractometer. The most abundant cations were Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺, while no appreciable concentrations of transition metal ions were detected. For the salt sample obtained at a recovery factor of 79 %, Ca²⁺ has the cation with the highest relative concentration (15.3 wt%), followed by Na⁺ (5.8 wt%), Mg²⁺ (0.6 wt%) and K⁺ (0.4 wt%). On the contrary, for the sample obtained at a recovery factor of 87 %, Na⁺ presented the highest concentration (21.8 wt%), while Ca²⁺ had a concentration of about 7 wt%. This confirms that calcium salts are the initial precipitates (before reaching a recovery factor of 79 %), followed by the predominant formation of NaCl crystals.

These data indicate that the MD process can potentially be controlled to target the sequential crystallization of salts based on their solubility and crystallization temperatures, enabling the separation and recovery of minerals from the mariculture effluent. This suggests that ZLD can be achieved through the methodology employed in this study. Currently, in ZLD systems, the solid waste produced is either deposited in landfills or recovered as valuable salt byproducts [43]. In the case of aquaculture effluents, the presence of non-volatile organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus, resulting from the dissolution of particulate organic components, hinders the recovery of pure salt via the MD process [44]. To recover salt by-products, further purification is necessary. On the other hand, direct disposal of the solid waste demands more thorough investigation to assess the environmental impacts of such materials, especially when scaled up, to ensure sustainability and environmental responsibility.

Fig. 7. XRD analysis of the salt crystals obtained by filtering the water in the MD feed tank at recovery factors of 79 % and 87 %. The characteristic peaks of halite (square) and gypsum (circle) were taken from the ICDD references n. 077-2064 and 21-0816, respectively.

4. Conclusions

This study explored the feasibility of using MD for desalinating inland mariculture effluent and employing a VUV/UVC photolysis reactor to detoxify the MD permeate. The MD system was tested at feed temperatures of 40 °C, 55 °C, and 70 °C, with recovery factors reaching up to approximately 90 %. In all tests, the MD process effectively achieved near-complete desalination, yielding a permeate with conductivity <100 μS cm⁻¹. Meanwhile, salt crystal formation was noted in the feed solution. The types of salt crystals produced by the MD process were primarily determined by the solubility of the salts and the water recovery factor achieved in the MD process. A threshold was observed at approximately 80 % of the recovery factor. Specifically, gypsum precipitated when the recovery rate was below 80 %, while NaCl began to precipitate once the recovery rate surpassed the 80 % mark. Although the MD technology demonstrated a high salt rejection, the membrane was permeable to HCHO, due to the volatile nature of this compound, compromising the reusability of the purified water. Our results showed that the photolysis could effectively degrade the HCHO from all permeated samples. More specifically, the concentration of the HCHO became undetectable within 20 min of the photolysis process. UV-based technologies are extensively utilized in aquaculture for disinfection purposes, demonstrating their effectiveness and widespread adoption in the existing facilities [45]. VUV/UVC treatments have proven to be highly effective in reducing pathogens and toxins that may develop in aquaculture facilities [46]. This suggests that VUV/UVC treatments hold significant potential for disinfection within our integrated system as well.

To the best of our knowledge, this study represents the first demonstration of integration between MD and with VUV/UVC photolysis for saline wastewater treatment. This streamlined two-step process can successfully recover fresh water, reclaiming solid waste, and degrading organic pollutants: all achieved without the need for extensive pre-treatment or the addition of chemicals. This approach sets a promising precedent for achieving zero liquid discharge in the aquaculture industry.

Funding

This research is part of two projects that have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, namely Project Ö (H2020-CIRC-2017TwoStage, Grant Agreement n. 776816) and SusWater (under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement N. 101007578).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Xianzheng Ma: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lana Flanjak:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **XinXin Chen:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Carmelo Morgante:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Bastian Stiem Kirkebæk:** Formal analysis. **Vittorio Boffa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Cejna Anna Quist-Jensen:** Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Aamer Ali:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Valter Maurino:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Peter Roslev:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank the European Commission for funding.

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